

Child Care Policy in Kazakhstan: A New Model

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Abstract : Child care policy must be a priority area of public authorities in any country. This study investigates child care policy in Kazakhstan in accordance with the current position of children and laws. The results show that Kazakhstan policy in this sphere needs more systematic model including state economic and social measures, parental involvement and role of non-government organizations.

Keywords : children, Kazakhstan, policy, vulnerability

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